

FACTORS DRIVING SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION OF CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT (CRM), BENEFITS SIGNIFICANCE AND FACTORS IMPACTING LONG TERM RELATIONSHIP – A STUDY W.R.T. SELECT COMMERCIAL BANKS AT BANGALORE.

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ABSTRACT

PURPOSE : The idea behind of these paper for analysing the demographical variables and its influence in the study of private banks in urban Bengaluru and to analyse the factors impacting the significance of CRM, factors driving successful implementation of CRM, benefits of CRM and factors driving the long term relationship between banker and customer. Commercial banks in India are contributing their might for the economic development and are highly useful in the poverty alleviation, employment creation and positively contributing towards GDP. The banking industry has steep competition and so all the financial institutions need to focus a strong relationship with customers for attaining the objective of customer relationship (Zakaria Ahmad Mohammed Assam, 2014).

APPROACH: A structural questionnaire was administered as schedule for the purpose of data collection. Chi-square contingency coefficient, Kendall's coefficient of concordance, ANOVA, and weighted average quantitative techniques were performed to analyse and present the data.

FINDINGS: In the present study there is a high degree of relationship between demographics and study on CRM. Operational inefficiencies are addressed through CRM and retention and acquisition of customers are driven by CRM. Further, the study also reveals globalisation of products requires CRM in the banks, and development of strong relationship is possible through CRM. Factors like attraction and retention of customers, customer focused organisation strategy, assessing accurate picture of customer category are impacting on successful implementation of CRM. The benefits from CRM found to be reduced customer switching, enhanced image of the organisation, more profitability etc.

The study also found the relationship between M- banking, Customer satisfaction and banker have capacity to understand the needs of the customer, which increasing persistent relationship between customer and banker.

KEYWORDS: *Image, unemployment, poverty alleviation, trust, loyalty, mobile banking, satisfaction, campaigns, customer categories, time value.*

INTRODUCTION

Innumerable changes are emerging in the banking business segment like introduction of ATMs, internet, ebanking, reduction of operational cost and increased speed of service. Still the management of customer relationship is a crucial issue in banking industry (Ndubisi, et al., 2007). Customers at present are more aware, knowledgeable, sophisticated, independent and are capable of negotiating with different service providers (Heinomen, 2014). Banks invest on the development of technology and human resources in order to develop customer relationship. The relationship must be such that both banking service providers and customers benefit from it on a long term (Dimitriadis, 2011), and consequently productivity and quality of banking service enhances based on the relationship between banker and customers (Brige, 2006). CRM is a concept for managing banks interactions with customers, clients, and sales prospects which can achieve financial institutions goal such as customer satisfaction (Zakaria Ahmed Mohammad Azzam, 2014).

CRM emerged due to raise in demand, changes in physiological of customers, their inclination, and changes in capital markets. To satisfy the needs of customers of present days the banks has to provide faster service which can be attained only when banks makes strong inclination towards customers (Jelena Cvijovic et al., 2017). CRM is a strategic process of business and not a technical one. Many organisations across the globe have realised that the objective of delivering better service, attaining more profitability and customer satisfaction can be attained through framing a workable and suitable to all CRM. The objective of CRM is to attain more profits, with the customers through better service, enhance the rate of profits. CRM systems have been adapted after understand customers needs (Kalaiarasi et al., 2019).

Customer satisfaction and maintaining eternal relationship are the two important reason for attaining profits. Research has revealed that dissatisfaction is the main factor of concern of bank customers interested in other banks (Manrai and Manrai, 2007).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Across the globe the private banks are facing stiff competition from government banks and non banking financial institutions. In order to survive and overcome the stiff competition banks should implement innovative strategies to retain and attract the customers, and to face the stiff competition. The development of the society depends upon the role of banking sectors and its essential role in the global economy and finance world. (Shailja Pal, 2018). Banking industry depends of trust, loyalty and relationship factors. On account of different apprehensions and reasons like financial burden, risk of failure, marketing inertia etc., still banks are following traditional ways of marketing and a few banks are making attempt to implement CRM. CRM benefits the banking industry in retaining the customers, understanding the needs of the modern customers, provides better ATM and mobile services and easy transfer of money. Since technology is a decision factor in rendering valuable service and forcing the banks to implement CRM. Attainment of large profits is also impacted by CRM based services in the banks and hence private sectors should opt revenue oriented CRM strategies. CRM attends the needs of customers without delay in the time and a royal treatment can be given through effective CRM.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Mehdi and Venkatesh (2011) investigate the obstacles for CRM implementation and analyse its practises in private and public banking industry in Iranian as per the process of management. The research focus that inadequate budget , less technical management support, lack of communication ,inadequate customer management skills are the main disadvantages of CRM implementation in public sector banks from private banks.

Rozita Shahbha (2012) reveal in his research that E-CRM has leverage like information space, up-to the minutes of Information of financial institutions, improve quality of service.

Jelena Cvijovic et al. (2017) stated that application of latest technologies, changes in capital market and customer inclination and behaviour increases the demand of CRM in banking industry. Further the researchers have stated that CRM give an opportunity to create friendly environment with customers and contributes loyalty to banks and increase the financial income for a long time.

Shailaja Pal (2018) expressed that for understanding individual customers instead of a group CRM play a vital role for managing the customers. The researcher further stated that CRM able to create the linkage between the organisation and customers. As per the researcher today many business houses like bankers, insurer, and other service providers realise the actual potential and capacity of CRM to acquire new customers,

Kalairasi et al. (2019) found in their study that CRM in banks assists for transformation in cultural, structural and business process in the firm. The researchers suggested that in the cutthroat environment Indian banking sector should select acceptable different marketing strategy and continuously follow the new services for the development of the banks

Karthikeyan N. (2020) stated that CRM over the last 10 years has become important. The competition has become highly competitive and it has become easy to customers to switch over to other organisations if they are not happy with the present type of service. The researcher further expressed that when the clients are managed and maintained properly, a company will be able to build relationship with their customers.

OBJECTIVES

- 1) To understand the impact of socio-economic characteristics in CRM.
- 2) To analyse the factors impacting the significance of CRM.
- 3) To study the factors driving successful implementation of CRM.
- 4) To analyse factors influencing long term relationship between private banks and customers.

HYPOTHESES

- 1) The respondents on economic social dimension are not influencing CRM in banks
- 2) There are no factors impacting the significance of CRM.
- 3) There are no factors driving successful implementation of CRM.
- 4) There are no benefits of CRM.
- 5) Factors are not influencing long life relationship between private banks and customers.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- 1) What are the factors on socio-economic characteristics not influencing the CRM
- 2) What are the factors, impacting the significance of CRM?
- 3) What are the factors driving successful implementation of CRM?
- 4) What are the benefits of CRM?
- 5) Which factors influences long life relationship between private banks and customers?

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Methodology refers to the method performed to present and analyse due data. Research design is a pre-planned activity pre projected for the future and it is in simplest terms refers to 'blue print', 'pre projected activity' and also it refers to array of conditions for collection and analysis of data. Research methodology is the specific technique used to recognise, select, process and analyse the information.

Sampling frame: The present study includes the sampling frame for data collection like Agriculturists 10, business people 22, freelance 10, salaried employees 40, professional 10 and house wives 8. The present

research convenient sampling technique was introduced and sample banks selected for the present study includes Yes Bank, HDFC and Axis Bank.

Data collection Instrument: Data collected through a proper well drafted, structural questionnaire and the study area is confined to Bangalore Urban. The two sections the questionnaire was divided and 1st section deals with demographics and 2nd part deals with analysis and Presentation of data.

Method of Data Analysis:

In this present study to measure the variations of the data different measuring techniques are used like χ^2 , contingency co-efficient, Kendall's co-efficient of concordance, ANOVA and weighted average technique useful in measuring the variations in the data evaluations and helpful in knowing the significant relationships between two related variables, where the weighted average measures the long term relationship and bank run customer.

LIMITATIONS:

- 1) To study is limited Bengaluru Urban.
- 2) Quantum of sample being less stipulated that any generalisation requires further in depth study.

ANALYSIS

The socio-economic characteristics based upon gender Income, Occupation, effectiveness of CRM and rating customers retention.

Research Question No. 1: What are the main factor behind socio economic characteristics not influencing on CRM?

Hypotheses No. 1 : There no significant difference in the socio-economic characteristics of respondents and they are not impacting the study.

H1 : There exist significant difference in the data and the socio-economic characteristics are impacting on the study.

There are 80 males and 20 females and 75 more married, 15 remained as single and 10 are divorcees. 33 respondents fall in the age group of 40-50, 25 in between 30-40 years, 18 are in the group of 20-30 years, 10 in between 50-60 years, 8 are above 60 years and 6 under 20 year, 33 respondents are post graduates, 26 degree holders, 15 studied up to PUC, 10 each studied up to 10th standard and professional degree holders and 6 ITI and other certificate holders. The study covered 40 salaried, 22 business people 10 each agriculture and professionals and further 10 are self employed and 8 are housewives. The income per month data reveals that 35 respondents are getting a monthly income in between Rs. 40K-50K, 25 respondents in between 30K-40K, 18 getting in between 20-30K, 12 are getting in between 10K-20K, 6 in between 50K-60K and 4 above 60K. As per the effect of customer relationship management as follows 45 expressed satisfaction, 42 good, 8 very good and 5 excellent. Further, the table reveals 52 are satisfied with the bank policy of retention of customers followed by 20 good rating, 15 very god, 13 excellent.

Table – 1 : Socio-Economic characteristics of respondents impacting on CRM

Characteristics	χ^2	TV@0.05 level	df	result of χ^2	'c'	Result of 'c'
Gender	36.00	3.841	1	Significant	0.51	High Degree
Marital Status	78.50	3.841	1	Significant	0.66	High Degree
Age in years	34.26	11.070	5	Significant	0.50	High Degree
Education	33.55	11.070	5	Significant	0.50	High Degree
Occupation	46.87	11.070	5	Significant	0.54	High Degree
Monthly income	42.19	11.070	5	Significant	0.54	High Degree
Effectiveness of CRM	55.12	7.815	3	Significant	0.59	High Degree
Rating customers retention	39.91	7.815	3	Significant	0.53	High Degree

Source : Field Survey

Note : χ^2 = chi-square

$$'c' = \sqrt{\frac{\chi^2}{\chi^2 + N}}$$

Where 'c' = contingency coefficient; N = Number of observations

When the value 'c' is equal or near 1, it means there is high degree of association between attributes. Contingency co-efficient will always to be less than 1.

Research question No. 2 : What are the factors impacting the significance of CRM?

Hypotheses No. 2 : H0 : There no significant difference in the factors influencing the significance of CRM.

H1 : There exist significant difference in the factors influencing significance of CRM.

Table – 2 highlights data on factors impacting the significance of CRM. 54 respondents out of 100 states strongly agree over the factors impacting on the significance of CRM followed by 31 agree, 15 somewhat agree. Out of 54 who said strongly agree, 15 spoke about retention and acquisition of customers that helps to face competition, 9 expressed about globalisation of bank products, 6 each reported about operational inefficiencies can be addressed and customers loyalty, retention and satisfaction are driven by CRM, 5 each felt about development of strong relationship between customer and banker and assessing the prospective customer. Out of 31 who said agree, 12 spoke about retention and acquisition of customers, 7 reported about globalisation of bank products and 3 each spoke about, addressing operational inefficiencies and customers retention loyalty are driven by CRM. Out of 15 respondents who said somewhat agree, 4 expressed about acquisition and retention, 3 spoke about globalisation bank products and 2 each reported about addressing the operational

inefficiencies. 'w' rejected H_0 and accept H_1 and hence there is need to focus the significant relationship between the factors and CRM.

Table - 2: Factors impacting the significance of CRM

Factors driving the significance of CRM	SA	A	SW A	RT	RT²
Retention and acquisition of customers which helps to face competition and survival	15	12	4	31	961
At the right time banks CRM assist to get prospective customers by providing right products	5	2	1	8	64
Development of strong and good relationship with the customers can be developed through CRM	5	2	1	8	64
Operational inefficiency can be addressed properly through good CRM strategies	6	3	2	11	121
Good distribution channel and management is possible by CRM technique	4	1	1	6	36
Customers are well informed by the implementation of better customer relationship management	4	1	2	7	49
Customers retention, loyalty and satisfaction are driven by CRM in a competitive environment	6	3	1	10	100
Globaliation of banks products and services CRM is must for the banking industry	9	7	3	19	361
Total	54	31	15	100	1756

Source : Field Survey

Note : SA – Strongly Agree, A – Agree, SWA – Somewhat Agree, RT – Row Total

$$SSR = \sum RT^2 - (\sum RT)^2 / N$$

$$= 1756 - (100^2) / 8 = 1756 - 1250 = 506$$

$$W = 12 \times SSR / K2N (N^2 - 1)$$

$$= 12 \times 506 / 9 \times 8 (64 - 1)$$

$$= 6072 / 4536 = 1.33$$

Test the significance of w by using the chi-square static.

$$X^2 = K (n-1) w$$

$$= 3 (8 - 1) \times 1.33$$

$$= 3 \times 7 \times 1.33 = 27.93$$

Decision : At 8 d.f. with 0.05 level of significance the TV = 15.507. The calculated value being 27.93 being higher than TV and hence ‘w’ rejected H0 and accepts H1. Therefore is needed that there exist significant relationship between the factors and CRM.

Research question No. 3: What are the factors driving successful implementation of CRM?

Hypotheses No. 3: H0 : There is no significant difference in the factors driving successful implementation of CRM?

H1 : There is a significant difference in the variable driving successful implementation of CRM.

Table – 3 highlights data regarding factors driving successful implementation of CRM. 64 respondents out of 100 stated strongly agree followed by 24 agree and 12 somewhat agree. Out of 64 who expressed strongly agree, 18 expressed about banks should know how to attract and retention the customers, 13 stated about customer focused organisation should be in operation, 11 felt about assess the accurate picture of customer categories, 8 reported about that banks should assess life time value of customer and 7 each are of the opinion that maximisation of profitability of each and every customer relationship, and on marketing campaigns banks should maximise the rate of return. Out of 24 who said agree, 6 each spoke about customer focused organisation should be in operation and banks should know how to attract and retain the customers, 4 reported about maximisation of profitability of each and every customer relationship. Out of 12 who stated somewhat agree 4 spoke about banks should know how to attract and retain the customers, 3 expressed about customer and 2 are of the opinion that on marketing campaigns banks should maximise the rate of return. ANOVA outcomes reject H₀ and accept H₁ and hence it is concluded that there need to focus in the variable successful implementation of CRM.

Table 3: Factors driving successful implementation of CRM

Factors driving successful implement of CRM	SA	A	SW A	T
Customer focused organisation should be in operation	13	6	3	22
Assess the accurate picture of customer categories	11	3	2	16
Banks should assess the life time value of customer	8	3	1	12
Maximisation of profitability of each and every customer relationship	7	4	1	12
Banks should know how to attract and retain the customers	18	6	4	28
On marketing campaigns banks should maximise the rate of return	7	2	1	10
Total	64	24	12	100

Source: Field Survey

Note: SA – Strongly Agree, A – Agree, SWA – Somewhat Agree, T – Total

Hypotheses

H0	There exist no significant variation in the data	Reject
H1	There exist significant variation in the data	Accept

ANOVA Table

Sources of variation	SS	df	MS	F-ratio	5% of limit (From F table)
Between the sample	247.3164	(3-1) = 2	247.3164/2 = 123.6582	123.6582/7.69 = 16.08	
Within the sample	115.3334	(18-3)= 15	115.3334 / 15 = 7.69		(2, 15) = 3.68
Total	362.6498	(18-1)=17			

Source : Field survey

ANOVA Analysis : The calculated value being 16.08 higher than the TV = 3.68 @ 5% level of significance with df = V1 = 2 and V2 = 18 fails to accept H₀ and accepts H₁ and hence it is concluded that there exist significant variations in the data.

Research question No. 4 : What are the benefits of CRM?

Hypotheses No. 4 : H₀ : There is no significant difference in the drivers of benefits of CRM.

H₁ : There is a significant difference in the drivers of benefits of CRM.

Table – 4 reveals data on factors driving significance of CRM. 58 respondents out of 100 expressed strongly agree over the statements driving the significance of CRM followed by 28 agree and 14 somewhat agree. Out of 58 respondents who stated strongly agree, 16 expressed about reduced customer switching, 11 stated about enhanced image of the organisation, 8 felt about more profitability, 7 opined about enhances customers loyalty, 6 stated about cross selling, and cross promotions and 5 each reported about repeat purchase and widened brand image. Out of 28 who said agree, 8 each stated about reduced customer switching and enhanced image of the organisation, 3 each felt about more profitability and enhances customer’s loyalty. Out of 14 who said somewhat agree, 5 stated about reduces customers switching and 4 felt about enhanced image of the organisation. ANOVA result reject H₀ and accepts H₁ and hence there need to focus in the drivers of benefits of CRM.

Table 4: Benefits from CRM

Factors driving benefits of CRM	SA	A	SWA	T
Reduced customers switching	16	8	5	29
Cross selling (selling related products) cross promotions (giving discounts) etc.,	6	2	2	10
More profitability	8	3	1	12
Enhances customer loyalty	7	3	1	11
Repeat purchase	5	2	-	7
Widened brand image	5	2	1	8
Enhanced image of the organisation	11	8	4	23
Total	58	28	14	100

Source : Field Survey

Note : SA – Strongly Agree, A – Agree, SWA – Somewhat Agree, T – Total

Hypotheses

H0	There exist no significant variation in the data	Reject
H1	There exist significant variation in the data	Accept

ANOVA Table

Sources of variation	SS	df	MS	F-ratio	5% of limit (From F table)
Between the sample	144.099 2	(3-1) = 2	144.0992/ 2 = 72.0496	72.0496 / 8.9682 = 8.03	
Within the sample	161.428 8	(21-3)= 18	161.4288 / 18 = 8.9682		(2, 18) = 3.55
Total	305.528 0	(21- 1)=20			

ANOVA Analysis : The calculated value being 8.03 higher than the TV = 3.55 @ 5% level of significance with $df = V1 = 2$ and $V2 = 18$ fails to accept H_0 and accepts H_1 and hence it is concluded that there exist significant variations in the data.

Research question No. 5 : Which variables influences lifelong relationship between private banks and customers?

Hypotheses No. 5 : H0 : There is no significant difference between the impact of lifelong relationship between private banks and customers

H1 : There is a significant difference between the impact of lifelong relationship between private banks and customers

Table – 5 explain the details about factors driving lifelong relationship between private banks and customers. 16 statements are influencing on the lifelong relationship between banks and customers. These factors vary from quick solving problems to customer satisfaction. Weighted average technique was performed with 5 point Likert scale varying from “strongly agree to strongly disagree”. The opinions of respondents (f) are multiplied by weights (w) to get ‘fw’. The weighted average (WA) is obtained. The table reveals customer satisfaction is the first highest factor impacting the long term relationship followed by second factor M- banking and capacity of banks to understand customer needs. The remaining factors are ranked depending upon the strength of ‘fw’.

Table – 5 : Factors influencing long term relationship between private banks and customers – weighted average

Factors	Weights	5	4	3	2	1	T	W A
	Likert	SA	A	N	D A	SD A		
Quick solving problems	f	55	18	9	8	10	100	26. 67
	fx	275	72	27	16	10	400	
Fast service	f	51	30	9	4	6	100	27. 73
	fx	255	120	27	8	6	416	
Attitude towards online service	F	45	32	9	8	6	100	26. 80
	fx	225	128	27	16	6	402	
Ability of banks to meet customer needs	f	72	19	4	3	2	100	30. 40
	fx	360	76	12	6	2	456	
Personal contact	f	35	32	18	7	8	100	25. 27
	fx	175	128	54	14	8	379	
Additional service	f	38	34	16	8	4	100	

	fx	190	136	48	16	4	394	26.. 27
Trust in the bank & its activities	f	45	25	12	10	8	100	25. 93
	fx	225	100	36	20	8	389	
Existing royalty and satisfaction	f	43	28	12	8	9	100	25. 87
	fx	215	112	36	16	9	388	
Customers knowledge of bank products and services	f	48	29	10	8	5	100	27. 13
	fx	240	116	30	16	5	407	
Efficient and valuable services	f	62	21	5	5	7	100	28. 40
	fx	310	84	15	10	7	426	
Response to need	f	45	28	10	8	9	100	26. 13
	fx	225	112	30	16	9	392	
Mobile banking	f	70	22	4	3	1	100	30. 47
	fx	350	88	12	6	1	457	
Well developed privacy policy	f	69	21	5	2	3	100	30. 06
	fx	345	84	15	4	3	451	
Art of retaining the existing customers	f	70	22	2	3	3	100	30. 06
	fx	350	88	6	6	3	436	
Use of effective communication tools	f	64	22	4	6	4	100	29. 06
	fx	340	88	12	12	4	436	
Customer satisfaction	f	71	24	2	2	1	100	30. 80
	fx	355	96	6	4	1	462	

Source: Field Survey

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSIONS

The current study for analysing the impact of demographics variable on Customer Relationship Management in commercials private banks at Bangalore. The research scholar and experts in the study emphasize more importance to the research work. The survey technique is included in the present study. The advance statistical tools like Kendall's co-efficient of concordance , ANOVA , Chi-square and weighted average is undertaken in the study. The result found that all the demographics revealed significant and high degree of relationship. Further, the result reveals about the factors influencing long term relationship between banker and customers, like customer satisfaction, M-banking and Banker have capacity to understand the need of the customers. The outcome also reveals that CRM significance is impacted by factors like, retention and acquisition of customers,

globalisation of bank products, customer's retention, loyalty and addressing operational inefficiencies. The finding also reveals that successful implementation of CRM in private commercial banks at Bengaluru is driven by banks should know the art of attracting and retaining the customer, customer focused organisation. The benefits of CRM includes reduced customer switching, enhanced image of the organisation, more profitability and enhanced customer loyalty and cross selling and cross promotions.

Based on the opinions that emerged at the time of data collection it was found some factors like retention and acquisition, globalisation of bank products, addressing operational inefficiencies are some of the factors which impacts on the significance of CRM and factors like attraction and retention of customers, customer focused organisation, about the accurate picture of customer contingencies etc., drives the successful implementation of CRM. The benefits of CRM includes reduced switching of customers, enhanced image of the organisation, more profitability are a few benefits of CRM. Convenient sampling technique was adopted while collecting the relevant data as per the questionnaire. However questionnaire was administered as schedule and a source of primary data while secondary sources includes E-journals and internet.

CONCLUSION

This paper is based on improving the use of CRM in private commercial banks at Bengaluru. Survivability of private commercial banks depends upon how best they render valuable service to the customers. The customers who are satisfied become faithful to the banks and give less interest to the other banks.

Private sector banks at Bengaluru providing better service on the one side and also facing competition from public sector banks on the other side. The recent trends in the commercial banks have shaken the customers and there is growing tendency among the public sector banks that customers are not cared properly. The lengthy queue and too much time in honouring cheques etc., are some of the weakness of public sector banks and these frauds are not found in the private sector banks. The study reveals about the better presence of demographics at Bengaluru and banks are following CRM strategies to benefit the customers, and to establish long term relationship. CRM facilities includes electronic fund transfer, card facility, mobile banking etc., The study reveals that factors like customer loyalty, cyber banking, and capacity of bank are some of the factors that drivers long term relationship between banker and customer.

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